

CITIZEN-SDSS PROJECT: Guidelines for conducting household-level interviews in mosaic forest landscapes of the Philippines

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Table of Contents

1	Background CITIZEN-SDSS Project	1
2	Objective of household surveys	1
3	General conventions household questionnaire (HHQ)	2
3.1	Selection of study sites and Barangays for conducting HHQ	2
3.2	Reference administrative boundaries study landscapes	2
3.3	Barangay	2
3.4	Barangay selection	2
3.5	Sampling using household lists and the total no. of interviewed HHs	3
3.6	The layout of the questionnaire	4
3.7	General guidelines when interviewing the respondent	4
3.8	Training and pre-testing	5
3.9	Data backup, sanitation and data entry	5
4	Definitions and terminologies	5
4.1	Household	5
4.2	Household head (HHQ section A3)	6
4.3	Georeferenced photos (HHQ section A3)	6
4.4	Forest ecosystem services (HHQ section B2)	6
4.5	Land degradation (HHQ section D)	7
4.6	Land use assets (HHQ section D)	7
4.7	Family labour (HHQ section E)	7
4.8	Household income (HHQ section E)	8
4.9	Income from agriculture and plantation activities (HHQ section E1)	8
4.10	Wage employed activities (HHQ section E4.1)	9
4.11	Income from off-farm self-employed/ business activities (HHQ section E4.2)	9
4.12	Other income sources (HHQ section E4.3)	9
5	Major land cover and land use types considered	9
5.1	Forest types	9
5.2	Timber plantations	10
5.3	Cropland	10
5.4	Pasture	10
5.5	Agroforestry	10
5.6	Fallow	10
5.7	Shrublands	10
5.8	Grassland	10
5.9	Wetlands	10
6	References	11

1 Background CITIZEN-SDSS Project

The remaining Philippine forest landscapes cover around 24% of the country's total land area. These landscapes are characterised by a high level of endemism, yet they are simultaneously threatened by deforestation and forest degradation, which has long-lasting effects on the ecosystem services they provide to society. Nature-based solutions (NBS) encompass a wide range of measures, such as forest conservation, reforestation, and restoration, and can support local livelihoods through community woodlots, agroforestry, and other initiatives, including living fences and riverbank vegetation. NBS have the potential to safeguard the Philippines' remaining forest landscapes and support national wood demand, which is currently met by industrial timber plantations and imports.

The CITIZEN-SDSS project aims to inform decision-making to support the development of long-term land use and forest management strategies that utilise nature-based solutions to sustain local livelihoods and ecosystem services. The project focuses on four study sites and their surrounding provinces - see for further details on study landscapes: Asare and Lippe (2025). The project combines participatory approaches and various forms of stakeholder interaction, such as key informant interviews, household interviews and focus group discussions, with geographic information systems (GIS) and spatiotemporal modelling. The latter can also be referred to as spatial decision support systems (SDSS). The project develops methodological approaches to make projections on long-term sustainable forest and land use management pathways, supporting local livelihoods and fostering nature-based solutions at Barangay level. This is important because decision-making processes require context-sensitive approaches that are also grounded in scientific rigour.

2 Objective of household surveys

The objective of the household survey is to collect information about the socio-economic profile of a household and its land use assets. Moreover, the survey aims to reveal households' perceptions on ecosystem services and land degradation, the role forests play in supporting local livelihoods at the Barangay-level, and to further assess how the Covid-19 pandemic influenced natural resource extractions.

In order to achieve this goal, household surveys are conducted in 6 villages for each of the four study landscapes of CITIZEN-SDSS (see **section 3.4** for more details). For data collection purposes, a structured questionnaire is used, commencing in a face-to-face situation, interviewing the household head as the primary respondent, and in case of his/ her absence, interviewing a household member (older than 18 years) to replace the household head. The latter one is then defined as a secondary respondent.

Furthermore, key informant interviews (KII) are conducted with the relevant Barangay captain or deputy to obtain information on the general demographic composition of a study Barangay, to collect information on local farm gate prices of the most relevant crops and non-farming products, among others.

The following sections provide instructions and explanations for enumerators in using the household questionnaire for conducting face-to-face interviews. This includes information on terminologies and conventions for the purpose of the household questionnaire (HHQ) and the CITIZEN-SDSS project. The document builds on several completed projects and their training guideline documents, and questionnaires, namely the Landscape Forestry in the Tropics (LaForeT) project ¹ and the related studies of Ojeda et al. (2020) and Wiebe et al. (2022), the Poverty Environment Network (PEN) project ² and the related studies of Angelsen et al. (2011) and prototype questionnaires and guidelines of PEN (2008), and the Thailand Vietnam Socio Economic Panel (TVSEP) ³,

¹ <https://www.la-foret.org/>

² <https://www2.cifor.org/pen>

³ <https://www.tvsep.de/en/>

and the related prototype questionnaires and guidelines of TVSEP (2024a, b, c). **Templates of the HHQ and KII are accompanying the guideline document and the open repository DOI (Zenodo, OpenAgrar).**

3 General conventions household questionnaire (HHQ)

The questionnaire is designed in a code-based tabular format. Thus, for almost all questions, a code list is presented from which answers have to be chosen or ticked by the enumerator. As it is, however, impossible to cover all answers via code lists, code option “90” allows the enumerator to add further items named “90=others, please specify”. In such a case, the enumerator has to write down “90” plus the missing/ new code item.

In general, it is important to try not to read out codes in front of the interviewed respondent, but instead to have a conversation where codes are discussed with the respondent. It is the enumerator's task to “encode” the respective answer to the HHQ. In this way, it should ensure the respondent’s attention during the interview, and avoid interview fatigue.

3.1 Selection of study sites and Barangays for conducting HHQ

The selection of the study area is a critical decision. The area is often chosen due to certain features of interest for the research project, which, in the case of CITIZEN-SDSS, refers to land degradation, nature-based solutions (e.g., agroforestry, forest conservation, reforestation), and ecosystem services provided by forests and locally prevailing other non-forest land use systems.

Due to financial and time constraints, it is usually not possible to include all Barangays of a certain municipality for household interviews. Thus, a selection is necessary that follows representativeness and context variability in key variables across the selected Barangays.

Given the overall project scope of CITIZEN-SDSS, 4 study sites were selected, with:

- Municipality of Penablanca and Balasig Watershed, being located in Region 2 Cagayan Valley, and
- Municipality of Silago and the City of Maasin are located in Region 8 Eastern Visayas.

3.2 Reference administrative boundaries study landscapes

For the purpose of study consistency, we rely on the administrative boundaries used at the level of municipality, independently of the administrative boundaries published by NAMRIA, DENR or other provincial or regional government agencies. When overlaying the different administrative boundaries in a GIS, inconsistencies among the various sources and agencies may occur and often become clearly visible. In such a case, it is not the task of the project to find agreement among the identified administrative boundary inconsistencies. Hence, the project relies on the administrative boundaries that are provided by the respective local government unit (LGU) or watershed boundary, given the research scope of CITIZEN-SDSS on LGU, respectively.

3.3 Barangay

For purposes of CITIZEN-SDSS research, a Barangay is defined as the lowest administrative unit in a study area, normally under the jurisdiction of a Barangay captain and other officials, such as the Barangay secretary.

3.4 Barangay selection

CITIZEN-SDSS relies on a stratified sampling approach for selecting a total of 6 Barangays per study (Municipality or Watershed) using land cover information from NAMRIA (2020), the most recent census data (PSA 2024), and the administrative boundaries of the selected municipalities of Maasin, Silago and Penablanca. For the case of the Balasig watershed, the hydrological boundaries defined by topographic features are used instead, which incorporates Barangays of the Municipalities of Cabagan and Tumauini.

Subsequently, the following calculation was done for each Barangay:

- 1) Calculate the area of forest and cropland per Barangay in hectare (ha),

- 2) Calculate the share of forest and cropland of a Barangay (ha) in relation to the total area of the Barangay (ha), and convert into %,
- 3) Use the results of (2.) to "sort" the barangays into three categories, namely:
 - a. "have cropland area but no forest area" (Category CROPLAND, **CL**),
 - b. "have more cropland area than forest area per total Barangay area" (Category CROP-FORESTLAND, **CFL**),
 - c. "have more forest area than cropland area per total Barangay area" (Category FOREST-CROPLAND, **FOCL**).

Based on this categorisation, **2 barangays are selected randomly per land cover category and study landscape, totalling 6 Barangays per study site, and 24 Barangays for all landscapes together (Table 1).**

Table 1. List of selected Barangays for each study landscape based on the predefined land cover categories (CROPLAND: CL, CROP-FORESTLAND: CFL, FOREST-CROPLAND: FOCL)

Study region	Study landscape	Name of Barangay	Land cover category	
Cagayan Valley	Balasig watershed	Union	CL	
		Pilig Alto	CL	
		Masipi East	FOCL	
	Municipality of Tumauni	Camasi	CFL	
		Cumabao	CFL	
		DY Abra	FOCL	
		Penablanca (Municipality)	Buyun	CFL
			Cabbo	CL
			Callao	CFL
	Eastern Visayas	Maasin (City)	Dodan	CL
			Minaga	FOCL
			Nanguilatan	FOCL
			Bactul I	CL
			Baugo	CFL
			Cagnituan	FOCL
Hantag			CL	
Lunas			FOCL	
San Jose			CLF	
Silago (Municipality)	Catmon	FOCL		
	Katipunan	FOCL		
	Tuba-on	CLF		
	Salvacion	CLF		
	Sap-ang	CL		
	Sudmon	CL		

3.5 Sampling using household lists and the total no. of interviewed HHs

The selection of households within a preselected Barangay is carried out using random sampling. This step is essential to ensure that the study sample is representative of the total population under investigation, defined here as all interviewed households across the four study sites. Random selection not only strengthens the validity

of conclusions drawn from the data but also facilitates subsequent statistical analysis by minimising bias and enhancing the reliability of comparisons.

For this purpose, household lists with the name of the household and, if available, the names of the other household members are required for a random selection of the target households per Barangay. For each land cover category (CL, CFL, FOCL), a target of 30 households is chosen, which requires interviewing a total of 90 households per study site.

Altogether, a total of 360 households were interviewed across the four study sites. To account for potential household dropouts or cases of unavailability during the survey period, the number of households randomly selected per Barangay was set at 20% above the target sample size. This oversampling strategy ensured that enumerators could replace unavailable households with preselected alternatives, thereby maintaining the intended sample size while preserving randomness and representativeness.

3.6 The layout of the questionnaire

The questionnaire contains different layout features to guide the enumerator:

- **Each question is continuously numbered**, and each answer has to be noted in the provided cells or tables. Continued numbering of questions later facilitates the entry of HHQ data into Excel data sheets.
- **Bold text** refers to particular remarks for enumerators and should not be overseen.
- **Coordinates** of the household location have to be either recorded in the format of “minutes, degrees, seconds” for Northing and Easting using either a handheld GPS device or a smartphone with a GPS recorder app.
- **Code lists** are provided for almost all questions, and they guide the enumerator in the conversation with the respondent, as well as to check whether certain issues were not (yet) mentioned by the respondent.
- **Time frames:** Many questions refer to a particular time frame, e.g., “during the past 12 months” or “in 2024”. Enumerators must ensure that the time frames are clearly communicated and understood by the respondent.
- **Amounts and percentages:** In some cases, it may be useful to first rely on local units (e.g., bags) rather than on the desired units of kilograms, hectares or m². If one uses local units, it is important to note such a calculation in the particular section of the HHQ. If respondents have difficulty providing amounts, enumerators should try to get a good estimate before skipping the question completely.

3.7 General guidelines when interviewing the respondent

General principles when interviewing a respondent can be summarised as “**listen, observe, and let the respondent talk**”. This further has to include:

- 1) Properly introduce yourself to the respondent and other attending household members before starting the interview.
- 2) Put the respondent at ease before starting the interview. Ask easier questions first, e.g., names of family or household members, before starting with the more difficult ones. Show genuine interest in the respondents.
- 3) In order to make the interview a pleasant experience and get good results, you should always be polite to the respondents and show interest in their stories.
- 4) A little small talk helps to get the conversation going. Especially when your respondents are nervous or shy, take a little time for a chat, so that everybody feels more relaxed and comfortable.
- 5) Do not ask questions simultaneously.
- 6) Do not read out codes in front of the interviewed respondent, but instead try to have a conversation where codes are discussed with the respondent. It is the enumerator to “encode” the respective answer to the HHQ, not the respondent him-/herself.

- 7) You may use indirect questions for sensitive aspects, e.g., income, ownership, disability, age, marital status, educational attainment, etc.
- 8) Be conscious of the time you conduct and the time spent on the interview.
- 9) Be patient. You will often encounter respondents who are unsure of the answer to certain questions. Explain to the respondents that there is no need to be insecure if they do not know the exact answers.
- 10) Try to get reliable estimations, e.g., by using a shorter recall period; otherwise, mark “99 = no answer”.
- 11) If an interview is difficult, resist the urge to skip questions and keep going through the questionnaire step by step, even if people do not know certain answers.
- 12) Completeness is a key criterion for high-quality information. So, use the questionnaire as a structured instrument to gather a complete data set.
- 13) Be critical. Sometimes respondents get bored during the interview and will just give you any answer to rush through the interview. If a respondent seems suspicious, use follow-up questions to check for consistency.
- 14) Be aware that some activities in the questionnaire may not be completely legal. A good relationship with the respondent may help to get some answers, but do not expect to obtain “the full truth and nothing but the truth”.
- 15) Sensitive questions: Keep in mind that respondents are free to skip certain questions if these are sensitive for them. While you should ask follow-up questions in some cases, you should not push too hard if your respondent is obviously uncomfortable.
- 16) Do not abuse respondents’ hospitality.
- 17) Do not interpret in front of the respondent.

3.8 Training and pre-testing

Training and pre-testing are important components of conducting successful HHQs, as they help to cross-check and test questionnaire settings under real-world situations, as well as to check whether certain questions and code lists are clear to the enumerator and respondent. In the case of CITIZEN-SDSS, several days of training were conducted at ISU and VSU, and at least two pretesting rounds took place, testing the HHQ with a total of 10 respondents who do not belong to any of the study areas.

3.9 Data backup, sanitation and data entry

- 1) **Data backup:** Each HHQ should back up twice: 1.) Taking photos of each HHQ page in the evening of an interview day, 2.) Uploading photos to the provided Google Drive folder after returning from a survey.
- 2) The information from the completed questionnaire should be checked by the enumerator directly after the interview for completeness and relevant immediate recall. The questionnaire has to be then given to an enumerator colleague who reviews the HHQ and checks all entries. As a next step, the responsible ISU/ VSU study leader will review the entries of the HHQ and approve data entry.
- 3) After **data entry is completed**, each HHQ questionnaire has to be **labelled and uploaded to the provided Google Drive folder**. Labelling has to be done as, e.g., *HHQID_MonthDayYear_FirstName_FamilyName*
- 4) **Data entry should be done on a regular basis and after returning from a field survey**. It should **NOT** be delayed towards the end of the overall interview period to ensure information consistency, and to allow for recall respondents in case of missing information or unclear entries.

4 Definitions and terminologies

4.1 Household

A **household** is defined as a “group of people (normally family members) living under the same roof, and pooling resources (labour and income)”.

Labour pooling means that household members exchange labour time without payment, e.g., on the farm or while running a business, such as a Sari-Sari store.

Income pooling means that all household members “eat from the same pot”, although some income may be kept by the household member who earns it. It is possible to have household members who are not blood relatives of the family, such as a household servant, an in-law, or someone taken into the household because they have been orphaned or otherwise destitute.

In most cases, the members of the household are easily identified, but here are some difficult cases:

- Several families living together in one house: If there is resource pooling, they should be treated as one household, otherwise not. An example: A married son still lives in the house of the parents. If his family’s economy is separated from the one of his parents (no income pooling, and they only occasionally eat together), they should be treated as two separate households.
- Family members living away parts of the time, e.g., working or going to school: Include if they are more or less fully integrated in the household economy (e.g., school children living away during the week, but parents paying for their expenses). In other cases, when children have left the house to work and take care of themselves, but contribute some income to the remaining household, they should NOT be included in the household. The money contributed should be recorded under remittances.
- In some situations, an extended family may be living in different houses, but sharing the same land and income, and eating most of their meals together. Again, following the household definition of “resource pooling”, the extended family should be treated as one household, although they don’t sleep under the same roof.
- One may have single person households, e.g., a widow living alone.

4.2 Household head (HHQ section A3)

The household head is typically well-defined by customary and/or official rules. In most cases, this would be the husband, but this might be more complicated if several generations are living together in the same household. Simply asking “who is the head of the household?” would normally solve the problem. In some contexts, the customary head is not the same as the official one, in which case one may choose to follow the customary rules.

4.3 Georeferenced photos (HHQ section A3)

Photos taken with a digital camera or smartphone can be linked to a geolocation. They should be taken in all directions of the compass or at a 90° angle to each other.

4.4 Forest ecosystem services (HHQ section B2)

Ecosystem services = The benefits people obtain from ecosystems. These include provisioning services such as food, timber, water, etc., regulating services that affect climate, flood control, disease, soil and water quality, etc., and cultural services that provide recreational, aesthetic, and spiritual benefits (Millennium Ecosystem Assessment, 2005).

Key ecosystem services considered:

- **Flood protection/ stormwater/sediment retention** This service also describes the capability of an ecosystem condition to prevent floods or obstruct the processes that lead to water runoff and inundation. They involve the ability of an ecosystem to absorb and store excess water during heavy rainfall events, reducing peak flows downstream and mitigating flood risk (Vári et al., 2022).
- **Soil conservation** Soil conservation ecosystem service can be described as the services that support the processes that maintain the quality, productivity, and stability of soil. This service involves the prevention or reduction of soil erosion,

- compaction, and loss of soil fertility, which safeguards soil health resources (Yin et al., 2022).
- **Climate regulation/
carbon sequestration** Carbon sequestration ecosystem service explains the process by which an ecosystem condition is able to remove carbon from the atmosphere and store it in various ecosystems (Davies et al., 2011).
 - **Habitat quality/
protection** The service describes the ability of ecosystems to provide suitable habitats that support the long-term presence of local populations of specific plant and animal species (Johnson, 2005; Liu et al., 2022).
 - **Sediment retention
and water quality** This service describes the ability of ecosystems to capture and hold sediments, preventing it from being transported by water flows into rivers and other water bodies (Vári et al., 2022).

4.5 Land degradation (HHQ section D)

The reduction or loss of the biological or economic productivity and complexity of rainfed cropland, irrigated cropland, or range, pasture, forest, and woodlands resulting from land uses or from a process or combination of processes, including processes arising from human activities and habitation patterns, such as: (i) Soil erosion caused by wind and/or water; (ii) deterioration of the physical, chemical, and biological or economic properties of soil; and (iii) long-term loss of natural vegetation. (UNCCD, 1994).

4.6 Land use assets (HHQ section D)

- Refer to the definitions of land cover/uses described in the Glossary. Make sure the enumerators clearly understand these.
- If households have several plots in the same category, e.g., cropland, and the plots may have different ownership statuses. One should then fill out the dominant ownership category (in terms of area).
- Some land, for example, pastures, may be shared with other households. Try to make a reasonable estimate of the respondent's share (and record that) based on, for example, the relative number of cattle grazing or the number of families sharing it.
- Some households do not know the size of their plots; others deliberately understate the size (particularly if taxation is based on land holding).
- If several couples are living together in the same household, one person might not be aware of the size of the other person's plot. It will be more accurate to ask each person about the size of his/her plot(s).

4.7 Family labour (HHQ section E)

Labour data are useful for a number of purposes, e.g., calculating the return to labour in different activities the household engages in. It takes, however, a lot of time to get reliable data, e.g., asking for each household member, for a number of tasks, and having short recall periods.

We measure the input of family labour in "person-hours". For person-hours, we must first ask for the average number of hours worked per day of the respective activity. Then we ask how many persons (family members) worked for how many days, and then calculate the total person-hours.

Examples for calculating person-hours:

- a) 5 family labourers work for 10 days, who work 8 hours per day on average, the person-hours are equal to 400 ($5 \times 10 \times 8 = 400$).
- b) 2 labourers who work for 10 days but only in the morning (5 hours), then the person-hours are $2 \times 10 \times 5 = 250$.

- c) The household states that he, his wife and his eldest son work for 3 days for the entire day (8 hours). In addition, the two youngest daughters, who still go to school, only help every afternoon after school. Both daughters worked 5 days for 4 hours per day. In this case, the total number for the parents and oldest son is $3 \times 3 \times 8 = 72$, and for the daughters $2 \times 5 \times 4 = 40$. All in all, the family works for 112 person-hours.

4.8 Household income (HHQ section E)

Income is generally defined as the value added of labour and capital (including land). The income of a household is therefore the return to the labour and capital it owns, used in its own production and income-generating activities (self-employment or business) or sold in a market (e.g., wage labour). We also include transfers in the income definition, such as remittances or pensions. Thus, income consists of three broad components:

- 1) Income (cash and subsistence) from self-employment and business.
- 2) Wage income and income from renting out capital (including land)
- 3) Transfers (e.g., pensions, remittances)

The basic income equation for income from self-employment or business (agriculture, forestry, and any other business) is:

$$I = \sum_{i=1}^n p_i y_i - \sum_{j=1}^m q_j v_j$$

Income (I) is gross value (price times quantities of all n products) minus the total costs (price times quantities) of all m purchased inputs (e.g., fertilisers, seeds, tools, hired labour, machinery, transportation and marketing costs).⁴ Note that the costs of family labour should NOT be deducted to obtain household income. One may want to measure the amounts and costs of family labour for other purposes, e.g., comparisons of the profitability of different activities, but it is not needed for calculating household income.

Total household income is the sum of cash income and subsistence income, the latter referring to the value of products being consumed directly by the household or given away to friends and relatives. One should be aware that many respondents may consider income to mean *cash income only*. **It is crucial that our expanded definition of income (subsistence + cash) is clear to both enumerators and respondents.**

4.9 Income from agriculture and plantation activities (HHQ section E1)

- It is important to note that this section includes both annual and perennial crops, as well as timber plantations, coconut plantations, banana, and abaca. Thus, **agroforestry, as well as trees-on-farm outputs (e.g., timber plantations, horticultural tree products)**, and their inputs are recorded. Also, crops grown in home gardens should be included here too. **All crops and plantations** grown on land not classified as forest should thus be included in this section.
- Valuable agricultural by-products should also be included, e.g., coconut lumber.

The area of production means the total area used for that crop or plantation. In the case of intercropping, enumerators should get a rough estimate of the *share devoted for each particular crop*. In other words, when adding up land area for each crop the total should correspond to the total land the household cultivates.

- Land that is rented in (borrowed / tenancy) falls in three categories which are treated as follows:
 1. The rental is paid for “in-kind” by giving the owner a share (*sharecropping*) or a certain amount of the output. The quantity of this production share should be reflected in question 50.8 “quantity sold (inc. barter / in kind)”.
 2. The rental is paid for in *cash*: the costs should be stated under “inputs” (question 51).
 3. *No rent* is paid: the table is filled out as if the borrower household owned it. There are no economic transactions in relation to the rental to be recorded.

⁴ Maintenance of capital stock (or depreciations) should also be included, but this will have limited applicability for most households.

- For inputs, the key is to get the total costs in order to calculate the net agricultural & plantation activities income. Thus, the respondent or farmer may, for example, use different types of seeds, but this is only relevant in order to estimate the total costs of seeds.

4.10 Wage employed activities (HHQ section E4.1)

- If the payment is (partly) in kind (e.g., helping in harvesting and getting paid 10 kg of rice), you should estimate the monetary value of that and include it as regular pay in the HHQ (question 54.5).

4.11 Income from off-farm self-employed/ business activities (HHQ section E4.2)

- By “own business” is meant that a person(s) in the household owns the business. In economic terms, ownership is usually defined as being the “residual claimant”, i.e., the owner has the right to the profit generated (what is left after all the expenses are deducted from the sales or services income). This could be, e.g., running a Sari-Sari shop, a barber shop, renting out machinery, or using a motorcycle as a taxi (=Tricycle).
- If the business is shared among several persons (households), the share to the members of the responding household should be reported (both for gross income and costs).
- Own non-labour inputs refer to, for example, agricultural products from the farm being used as inputs in the business. The equivalent market value should then be stated.

4.12 Other income sources (HHQ section E4.3)

- **Remittances** refer to money transfers from family members that are not part of the household, e.g., OFW or domestic.
- **Smaller gifts from friends and relatives** (less than 500 PHP) should NOT be included, e.g., a chicken given as part of a reciprocal system. This question is meant to capture the larger unilateral transfers, e.g., a widow who survives on the support she receives from her neighbours.
- Payment for services, e.g., forest patrolling, should be specified here.

5 Major land cover and land use types considered

Land cover = the observed (bio)physical cover on the earth's surface

Land use = characterised by the arrangements, activities and inputs people undertake in a certain land cover type to produce, change or maintain it. Some examples to explain the difference between land cover and land use:

- "grassland" is a land cover term, while "rangeland" or "football field" refers to the use of a grass cover;
- “broad-leaf closed canopy forest” is a land cover term, while “a logged-over forest” refers to the use of a forest cover for timber extraction; “cropland” is a land cover term, while “irrigated rice” or “maize intercropping” refers to the management and use of croplands.

5.1 Forest types

We distinguish between natural and secondary forest with the primary criterion as the *degree of human intervention*:

1. **Natural forest** (old growth) consists of indigenous (native) tree species. It is managed only to a very limited degree, i.e., one may practice “tolerant forest management in which the native vegetation is largely conserved or reconstructed through successional processes”.

In natural forests, most beneficial trees occur spontaneously, although there may be some degree of management to stimulate the frequency and growth of these trees, e.g., by clearing competing vegetation.

2. **Secondary forest** consists predominantly of indigenous vegetation and has been selectively logged or completely deforested in the past. Potential signs of logging, such as tree stumps or logs, might still be visible.

5.2 Timber plantations

Timber plantations consist of tree stands established by planting and/or seeding in the process of afforestation or reforestation. They are composed either of (a) introduced species (all planted stands), or (b) intensively managed stands of indigenous species, which meet all the following criteria: one or two tree species planted, even age class, regular spacing.

5.3 Cropland

Cropland is defined as land from which crops are harvested. A few exceptions are worth pointing out:

- Idle cropland, i.e., land which is normally used for crops but temporarily not cropped, should be included under **fallow**.
- Land with trees grown for wood or timber should be categorised as a **plantation**.
- Annual/ perennial crops cultivated in combination with trees (and animals) should be categorised as an **agroforest**.

5.4 Pasture

Pasture is generally referred to as land covered with grass or other vegetation (herbaceous forage crops) eaten by grazing domesticated animals. Pastures can cover land where grasses and/or legumes have been established by humans and/or involve some form of active management (pasture managed; pasture non-managed).

5.5 Agroforestry

Agroforestry is defined as “an agricultural land use that combines growing trees (woody perennials) with annual (*herbaceous*) crops, either on a spatial or temporal scale.” Note that agroforestry is characterized both by the type of vegetation (mix of trees and annual crops) and the intentional establishment of this system by humans for agricultural purposes. A subcategory of agroforestry refers the combination of trees and pasture (with crops = Agrosilvipasture/ without crops = Silvipasture). To qualify as a silvipasture system, either the trees or the pasture (or both) must have been established by humans.

5.6 Fallow

Fallow land refers to agricultural land, that is, it has been used for growing agricultural crops and/or pasture within the last 15 years, and is it likely to be used for cropping/livestock again in the short/medium term.

5.7 Shrublands

Shrubs “refer to vegetation types where the dominant woody elements are woody perennial plants, generally of more than 0.5 m and less than 5 m in height on maturity and without a definite crown.” Thus, woody vegetation is broadly classified into forest and shrubs, where a plant height of 5 meters draws the line. Shrubs with a closed canopy are referred to as *thicket*.

5.8 Grassland

Grassland has naturally occurred grass as the predominant vegetation. If it has trees scattered around (and canopy cover below 10 %), it is referred to as *wooded grassland*. Grassland may be used for grazing domestic animals, and may then be referred to as *pasture*.

5.9 Wetlands

Wetlands refer to land areas where water saturates the soil, either permanently (*swamp*) or parts of the year. If a wetland is used for agriculture, e.g., for paddy rice, it should be included in one of the agricultural land categories.

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